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Annotation. *Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a leading cause of premature mortality and disability. Despite a significant number of drugs, the effectiveness of therapy aimed at normalizing glycemic levels and preventing complications does not fully satisfy doctors and patients. Therefore, the search for new approaches for the prevention and treatment of diabetes and its complications continues. Significant resources are used to develop new drugs, but recently the possibility of using “old” widely available drugs with newly discovered pleiotropic properties has been justified. These may include gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) preparations and agents that directly or indirectly activate GABAergic transmission, which have a pronounced pancreoprotective effect, which has been widely discussed in foreign literature in the last 10–15 years. However, there are few such publications in the domestic literature. It has been established that the content of GABA in β -cells in patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes decreases, and this correlates with the severity of the disease. Genetic suppression of GABA_A receptors causes a significant decrease in β -cell mass and glucose-stimulated insulin secretion, which confirms the importance of GABA in ensuring glucose homeostasis and the advisability of replenishing GABA deficiency in diabetes with its additional administration. It has been established that in animals with diabetes, GABA suppresses apoptosis and stimulates the regeneration of β -cells, increases β -cell mass and insulin production. Experimental data have been obtained indicating the synergistic effect of GABA when combined with glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptor agonists, dipeptidyl peptidase type 4 (DPP-4) inhibitors and sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT-2) inhibitors, when a more pronounced pancreoprotective effect is observed, due to a decrease in oxidative and nitrosative stress, inflammation, an increase in the level of Klotho protein, Nrf-2 activity and antioxidant defense enzymes, suppression of NF- κ B activity and the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines. As a result, all this leads to a decrease in apoptosis and death of β -cells, an increase in β -cell mass, insulin production and at the same time a decrease in glucagon levels, insulin resistance.*

KEYWORDS: *GABA; β cells, α cells, diabetes, insulin, enzymes, DPP-4.*

ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЕ ГАМК И ГИПОГЛИКЕМИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ*Давранова Азиза Даврановна**Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет
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Аннотация. Сахарный диабет (СД) является ведущей причиной преждевременной смертности и инвалидности. Несмотря на значительное количество препаратов, эффективность терапии, направленной на нормализацию уровня гликемии и предотвращение осложнений, не в полной мере удовлетворяет врачей и пациентов. Поэтому поиск новых подходов к профилактике и лечению сахарного диабета и его осложнений продолжается. На разработку новых лекарств тратятся значительные ресурсы, но в последнее время обоснована возможность использования «старых», широко доступных препаратов с вновь открытыми плейотропными свойствами. К ним можно отнести препараты гамма-аминомасляной кислоты (ГАМК) и средства, прямо или косвенно активирующие ГАМКергическую передачу, обладающие выраженным панкреопротекторным действием, что широко обсуждается в зарубежной литературе в последние 10–15 лет. Однако подобных публикаций в отечественной литературе немного. Установлено, что содержание ГАМК в β -клетках у больных сахарным диабетом 1 и 2 типа снижается, и это коррелирует с тяжестью заболевания. Генетическая супрессия ГАМК-рецепторов вызывает значительное снижение массы β -клеток и глюкозо-стимулируемую секрецию инсулина, что подтверждает значение ГАМК в обеспечении гомеостаза глюкозы и целесообразность восполнения дефицита ГАМК при сахарном диабете с помощью ее дополнительного введения. Установлено, что у животных с сахарным диабетом ГАМК подавляет апоптоз и стимулирует регенерацию β -клеток, увеличивает массу β -клеток и продукцию инсулина. Получены экспериментальные данные, указывающие на синергический эффект ГАМК при сочетании с агонистами рецепторов глюкагоноподобного пептида-1 (ГПП-1), ингибиторами дипептидилпептидазы 4-го типа (ДПП-4) и ингибиторами натрий-глюкозного котранспортера 2 (SGLT-2). , когда наблюдается более выраженный панкреопротекторный эффект за счет снижения окислительного и нитрозативного стресса, воспаления, повышения уровня белка Клото, активности Nrf-2 и ферментов антиоксидантной защиты, подавления активности NF-kB и экспрессии провоспалительные цитокины. В результате все это приводит к уменьшению апоптоза и гибели β -клеток, увеличению массы β -клеток, выработке инсулина и одновременно снижению уровня глюкагона, инсулинорезистентности.

Ключевые слова: ГАМК; β -клетки, α -клетки, диабет, инсулин, ферменты, ДПП-4.

Introduction. Diabetes mellitus (DM), due to its widespread prevalence and severity of complications, is a major medical, social and economic problem [1]. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number of patients with diabetes has more than doubled over the past 20 years: according to the register of patients with diabetes, as of January 1, 2021, 4,799,552 (3.23%) patients were registered at the dispensary [2]. According to forecasts of the International Diabetes Association, the number of patients with diabetes will reach 642 million people by 2040 [2]. The use of modern drugs has significantly improved the quality of life of people suffering from diabetes. However, in more than 2/3 of patients it is not possible to achieve target glycemic values, and it is also not always possible to prevent the loss of pancreatic β -cells and numerous complications of diabetes. This encourages the search for new targets and new drugs, the use of combination therapy, and the development of new strategies and new technologies for the treatment of diabetes [1, 3, 4]. Types 1 and 2 diabetes are associated with progressive death of β -cells with the participation of the immune system and inflammation, oxidative and nitrosative stress, glucose and lipotoxicity. One of the areas of treatment for diabetes is the use of drugs that suppress apoptosis and death of β -cells and activate their proliferation and regeneration, increasing insulin production [5–9]. Such properties were noted in incretins, gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), inhibitors of sodium-glucose cotransporter type 2 (NGLT-2), etc., but with monotherapy it is not always possible to achieve normoglycemia, reduce apoptosis and death of β -cells, and enhance their regeneration and increase in β -cell mass, prevent the development of complications of diabetes [9]. In order to increase the effectiveness of antidiabetic therapy for diabetes, a combination of 2 or even 3 hypoglycemic drugs that give a synergistic effect is widely used [4, 10]. In recent years, a number of studies have been published on the synergistic effect of GABA and some hypoglycemic agents of the latest generation, reflecting their effect on glucose homeostasis, the functioning of β -cells, and the formation of additional positive therapeutic effects [9]. In this review, we present data demonstrating the synergistic interaction of GABA and drugs with GABAergic action in combination with drugs that have an incretin-like effect: glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonists (GLP-1R), dipeptidyl peptidase 4 (DPP-4) inhibitors and NGLT- 2, having previously considered their class-specific properties, including pleiotropic ones. The search was carried out in the Pubmed, eLibrary, Medline databases using the keywords: diabetes mellitus, gamma-aminobutyric acid, glucagon-like peptide-1, GLP-1R agonists, glucose-dependent insulinotropic peptide (GIP), dipeptidyl peptidase

inhibitors, sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors. The search was carried out over the period from 2021 to 2023, but the review presents the results of studies published mainly over the last 3 years, which is due to the journal's requirements for the maximum volume of work and the number of sources.

Role of gaba in the regulation of carbohydrate metabolism. Since the discovery of GABA and its inhibitory properties in the brain (BM), much of our understanding of its physiological role has changed significantly. It was found that GABA is detected in almost all tissues and organs. In pancreatic tissues, the GABA content is comparable to that in the GM and is highly expressed in α - and β -cells of the islets of Langerhans [6, 11]. The GABA content in β -cells in patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes decreases, and insulin secretion is impaired [12, 13]. This supports the contention that loss of GABA correlates with the pathogenesis of diabetes [8]. In the pancreatic islets, insulin-producing β -cells express GABAA and GABA B receptors, which are encoded by different intracellular pathways and form different signal transduction mechanisms [6, 12, 14, 15]. Once released, GABA influences the activity of α - and β -cells of the pancreas through ionotropic GABAA receptors and metabotropic GABAB receptors. The effect of GABA on α - and β -cells differs; on the former it has an inhibitory effect, reducing the production and release of glucagon, on β -cells it has a stimulating effect, increasing insulin secretion [15]. GABA in pancreatic β -cells through GABA A receptors activates calcium-dependent signaling pathways and voltage-dependent channels, triggers the PI3K/Akt, CREB-IRS-2 and SIRT-1 signaling cascades, which may be decisive in the regulation of mass and functions β -cells [11, 15]. Obesity plays a key role in the development of insulin resistance, diabetes and its complications [16, 17]. Therefore, reducing insulin resistance is an independent task for the prevention and treatment of diabetes. GABA has therapeutic potential against obesity, which is associated with the suppression of oxidative stress and endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress. GABA reduced the expression of the adipogenic transcription factor PPAR- γ in the adipose tissue and liver of mice fed a fat-rich, high-calorie diet. GABA controls the activity of NADPH oxidase (NOX4) during dysmetabolism associated with high-fat and carbohydrate-rich foods, causing the breakdown of IRE-1a, which sulfonates RIDD-SIRT. Administration of GABA significantly increased AMPK and SIRT-1 levels in obese mice [17], decreased insulin resistance, increased liver glycogen levels, improved lipid profile, and decreased glucose and glycated hemoglobin levels [18, 19]. GABA significantly reduced insulin resistance by activating the expression of the glucose transporter gene (GLUT-4), suppressing

the gluconeogenesis pathway in the liver, reducing the expression of the FOXO1 and Pepck genes, and simultaneously increasing the expression of the IRS-2 and Akt2 genes [18]. GABA stimulates phosphorylation of CREB through cAMP element binding protein (AMPK), known as a key transcription factor responsible for insulin gene maintenance and β -cell survival, thereby promoting increased β -cell mass. The trophic effects of GABA are formed through the activation of the Akt and CREB signaling pathways independently of each other, but activation of both pathways is required for an optimal response. The involvement of Ca^{2+} and CREB and their glucose-dependent activation of β -cell IRS-2 is important for the plasticity of the β -cell response to increased insulin demand. GABA-induced activation of CREB is simultaneously associated with increased levels of IRS-2 transcript expression [6, 15, 20]. The role of the GABAergic system in the regulation of carbohydrate metabolism is also confirmed by the fact that genetic suppression of GABA receptors significantly reduced the mass of β -cells and glucose-stimulated insulin secretion, which led to disruption of glucose homeostasis [8, 9].

Conclusion. The development of innovative drugs requires significant resources. An alternative to this could be the identification of new targets for already known drugs, which open up other indications and prospects for their use in complex therapy. These may include GABA and drugs with GABAergic action, which, judging by many publications, can improve the functional state of β -cells, reduce oxidative stress and inflammation. Currently, data have accumulated on the synergistic effect of GABA when combined with GLP-1R agonists, DPP-4 inhibitors and SGLT-2 inhibitors with increased pancreatic protective action, which is due to a decrease in oxidative stress and inflammation, an increase in the level of Klotho protein, Nrf-2 activity and antioxidant defense enzymes, suppression of NF-kB activity and the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines. This led to a decrease in β -cell death, an increase in β -cell mass, insulin production, and at the same time a decrease in insulin resistance.

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